

ARIES

Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 730871

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Report on advances in beam diagnostics for Free-Electron Lasers (FELs)

DELIVERABLE: D8.4

Document identifier:	ARIES-D8.4
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 54 (September 2021)
Justification for delay:	Delay related to COVID-19 pandemic concerning workshop organization
Report release date:	2012/2021
Work package:	WP8: Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerators (ADA)
Lead beneficiary:	DESY
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

Section 6 of this Report covers the subject of Deliverable 8.4 (Advances in beam diagnostics for FELs). Sections 6.1 to 6.2 summarize the two International Workshops organised on this specific subject, and Section 6.3 presents some general conclusions on the status of this field and on possible future developments. In the Appendix, detailed descriptions of the three Workshops concerned are given.

ARIES Work Package 8 aims for transfer of knowledge and standardisation of equipment across the European Research Infrastructures making use of beam instrumentation and diagnostics for particle accelerators. In total, 11 International Workshops were organized with 32 to 239 delegates (maximum for a remote workshop). Financial support for visits of scientists was covered in total for eight weeks.

While in the initial Work Plan it was foreseen to produce as a Deliverable four separated Reports, one for each of the Tasks/sub-sets of diagnostic equipment, during the execution of the project it turned out the number of intercorrelations and crossed references between the four areas was so large that it was more effective to produce a single report, with four Sections each devoted to one of the Tasks/Deliverables.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors, please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730871. ARIES began in May 2017 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	P. Forck	GSI	16/12/21
Edited by	P. Forck	GSI	16/12/21
Reviewed by	M. Vretenar on behalf of Steering Committee	CERN	17/12/21
Approved by	Project Coordinator		20/12/21

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. TASK 1 ON WORK-PACKAGE COORDINATION.....	8
3. PROGRESS IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR HADRON LINACS (TASK 2).....	9
3.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘SIMULATION, DESIGN & OPERATION OF IONIZATION PROFILE MONITORS’	9
3.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘SCINTILLATION SCREENS AND OPTICAL TECHNOLOGY FOR TRANSVERSE PROFILE MEASUREMENTS’	9
3.3 WORKSHOP ON ‘EXPERIENCES DURING HADRON LINAC COMMISSIONING.’	10
3.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	11
4. ADVANCES IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR HADRON SYNCHROTRONS (TASK 3)	13
4.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘EXTRACTING INFORMATION FROM ELECTROMAGNETIC MONITORS IN HADRON ACCELERATORS’ ..	13
4.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS’	13
4.3 WORKSHOP ON ‘MATERIALS AND ENGINEERING FOR PARTICLE ACCELERATOR BEAM DIAGNOSTIC INSTRUMENTS’	14
4.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	16
5. ADVANCES IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR 3RD GENERATION LIGHT SOURCES (TASK 4)18	
5.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS’	18
5.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 19)’	18
5.3 WORKSHOP ON ‘DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 21)’	18
5.4 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	19
6. ADVANCES IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR FREE ELECTRON LASERS AND ELECTRON LINACS (TASK5)	21
6.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘EMITTANCE MEASUREMENTS FOR LIGHT SOURCES AND FELs’	21
6.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘LONGITUDINAL DIAGNOSTICS AT FREE ELECTRON LASERS’	21
6.3 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	22
7. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK	24
8. REFERENCES	25
9. ATTACHMENTS.....	25

Executive summary

To meet the demands of new accelerator facilities, novel beam instrumentation and diagnostics methods are required. Beam instrumentation deals with versatile topics of applied physics and various technologies. The network 'Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerator' (ARIES-ADA) focused activities at various laboratories to initialize collaborations on a formal or, in most cases, informal basis. As a methodology, topical workshops related to one actual subject was chosen; moreover, the exchange of personnel between accelerator laboratories and universities is covered financially. Eleven topical workshops were organized; all workshops had participants from America, Asia and Europe. In three of these workshops, ARIES-ADA acts as a co-sponsor, leading to increasing contributions. Eight of these topical workshops were organized as a high-light event; each covers a topic that is not discussed in such detail at conferences and contributed significantly to a knowledge transfer between experts in various fields.

Eight of the workshops were executed as an in-person meeting between May 2017 and June 2019; depending on the subject, the number of delegates varied from 32 to 84. Personal contact is the key issue for sustainable collaborations, and those workshops contribute significantly to their initialization. The workshop duration was between one and three full days. The financial budget of ARIES-ADA was used to cover part of the costs of the workshops.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic initialized travel restrictions started in spring 2020, three workshops were organized as remote events between three and five half-days. The number of registrants was higher than the in-person meetings and increasing contributions.

In addition to the workshops, the budget was used to finance personnel exchanges for three scientists and duration between two and four weeks. In particular, early-stage scientists benefitted significantly. Several further visits were planned but could not be realized due to the travel restrictions that showed up at the end of 2019.

In contrary to the planned initially categories related to the different types of accelerators (hadron LINAC, hadron synchrotrons, circular light sources and linear light sources), it turned out that it is much more efficient to discuss in a common report the challenges related to various diagnostics methods, gaining from the synergy between the communities. Consequently, one more comprehensive deliverable report instead of four separate reports has been produced. The workshop content is shortly described in the main text, and detailed summaries of each workshop are attached as an appendix.

The subject of Deliverable 8.4 is therefore covered in Section 6 of the present Report.

1. Introduction

To meet the demands of new accelerator facilities, novel beam instrumentation and diagnostics methods are required leading to the permanent development of beam instruments. Versatile technologies are used based on many aspects of applied physics. The knowledge transfer between accelerator laboratories, universities, and industry is the focus of the ARIES work-package 8 network activity called ‘Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerator’ (ARIES-ADA). As the methodology, the organization of topical workshops related to one dedicated topic was chosen, offering the possibility of in-depth discussion on one subject not covered at typical conferences in such detail. A further aim is to initialize or intensify collaboration between the laboratories and strengthen the contact to industry for joint developments and efficient usage of available human resources. The industry is a relevant partner and contributed to several scientific talks the workshops.

Initially, it was planned to divide the work package into four tasks, namely related to hadron LINACs (Task 2 led by GSI), hadron synchrotrons (Task 3 led by CERN), circular synchrotron light source (Task 4 led by ALBA) and linear FEL light sources (Task 5 led by DESY). During the work-package execution, it turned out that this is not an efficient classification as most of the actual workshop topics comparably concerned several tasks. Due to this change of perspective, the planned initially individual Deliverable Reports D8.1 to D8.4 are now combined in a lengthy report covering the entire work-package program.

Eleven topical workshops were organized; all workshops had participants from America, Asia and Europe. Table 1 contains the compilation of the workshops, including the links to the INDICO site and some basic numbers cornering the duration, number of participants etc. For three of these workshops, ARIES-ADA acts as a co-sponsor, allowing for an increase of contributions. Eight of these topical workshops were organized as a high-light event; each covers an actual topic, which is not covered in such detail at typical conferences. The program ARIES-ADA contributed significantly to the knowledge transfer between experts in various fields in science and technology. In particular, engineers participated in those workshops, who usually are not contributing to regular conferences.

Eight of the workshops were executed as in-person meetings between May 2017 and June 2019; depending on the subject, the number of delegates varied from 32 to 84. Personal contact is the key issue for sustainable collaborations, and those workshops contribute significantly to their initialization. The workshop duration was between one and three full days. The financial budget of ARIES-ADA was used to cover part of the workshops costs and contributed to the travel costs of the workshop attendees. This allows for the participation of not only physicist but also engineers and technical personnel and people from outside of Europe where the home institutes might now be able to cover the full travel cost.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic initialized travel restrictions starting in spring 2020, three workshops were organized as remote workshops with a duration of between three and five half-days. The number of registrants was higher than in-person meetings, namely 49, 205 and 239. About 100 people were connected simultaneously during the presentation sessions for the last two workshops. The easier access without travels disabled a wider variety of contributions presented to a broader audience.

Personal discussions were still possible, in particular, when separated 'breakout rooms' were prepared beforehand by the workshop organizers.

Table 1: Compilation of topical workshops organized within the frame of ARIES-ADA; the columns are the date, main organizer, location of the workshop, title (linked to workshop INDICO-site), number of delegates the task which is mainly concerned and co-organizing tasks.

#	Date	Org. & location	Title of workshop	# Part.	main task	Contr. task
1	22-24 May 2017	GSI Darmstadt	<u>Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors</u>	33	2	3
2	29-30 Jan. 2018	ALBA & DESY Barcelona	<u>Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs</u>	37	5	4
3	14-16 May 2018	CERN & GSI Geneva	<u>Extracting information from electromagnetic monitors in Hadron Accelerators</u>	32	3	4
4	25-27 June 2018	DESY & PSI Hamburg	<u>Longitudinal Diagnostics at FELs</u> (co-sponsoring)	45	5	-
5 & 6	12-14 Nov. 2018	ALBA & GSI Barcelona	<u>Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems</u> Two in one event: hadron & electron acc.	84	3 & 4	-
7	1-3 April 2019	GSI & SOLARIS Krakow	<u>Scintillation Screens and Optical Technology for transverse Profile Measurements</u>	49	2	4 & 5
8	3-5 June 2019	ALBA & ESRF Grenoble	<u>Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources (DEELS 19)</u> (co-sponsoring)	33	4	
9	25-29 Jan. 2021	CIEMAT & GSI Online	<u>Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning</u>	239	2	
10	21-23 June 2021	CERN & GSI Online	<u>Materials and Engineering for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments</u>	205	3	2, 4 & 5
11	7-8 July 2021	ALBA & SESAME Online	<u>Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources (DEELS 21)</u> (co-sponsoring)	49	4	

Table 1 summarises the subjects of the workshops, including some basic numbers, such as the duration, the number of delegates, link to the workshop INDICO-site and the involved ARIES-ADA tasks. Several of the workshops were summarised at the beam instrumentation conference IBIC series for a larger audience, showing the relevance of the discussed projects and the importance of the funding by the European Community; clear credits are given to the EU funding. The related papers are:

- Invited talk at IBIC 2018 by Ubaldo Iriso: “Summary of Emittance Measurements Workshop for SLS and FELs”; no proceedings were written.
- Poster contribution at IBIC 2018 by Peter Forck: “ARIES-ADA: An R&D Network for Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerators”; related conference proceeding Ref. [1].

- Invited talk at IBIC 2019 by Beata Walasek-Höhne: “Screens for High Precision Measurements”; related conference proceeding Ref. [2].
- Invited talk at IBIC 2019 by Guenther Rehm: "Characterization of Closed Orbit Feedback Systems”; related conference proceeding Ref. [3].
- Contributed talk at IBIC 2021 by Peter Forck: “Summary of the ARIES Workshop on Materials and Engineering Technologies for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments”; related conference proceeding Ref. [4].

Most of the ARIES-ADA budget was used to cover the event costs such as venue rent, the cost for coffee breaks and refreshments and administrative issues. Some parts of the travel costs for delegates were covered; this enabled the participation of young scientists and people from institutes with a low amount of travel budget, increasing the intentionality of the events.

In addition to the workshops, the ARIES-ADA budget was used to finance the personnel exchanges for three scientists and duration between two and four weeks. In all cases, a relation to one of the workshop subjects exists. In particular, early-stage scientists benefitted significantly. The involved institutions were:

- A scientist from Fermilab (USA) visited GSI related to Ionization Profile Monitor development
- A scientist from the University of Milan visited ALBA related to high-resolution profile measurement at light sources
- A scientist from GSI visited Diamond Light Source related to the closed orbit feedback design at synchrotrons; this scientific discussion contributed to peer-reviewed journal articles Ref. [5, 6].

Several further visits were scheduled but could not be realized due to the travel restrictions that showed up at the end of 2019. It concerned visits of a Chinese scientist from IMP at GSI, a Jordanian scientist from SESAME at ALBA, two German scientists from GSI to the Brazilian light source SIRIUS.

Generally, the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the exchange of personnel, resulting in the complete cancellation of visits from the beginning of the year 2020. Workshops were foreseen as in-person events to enable a familiar atmosphere with senior people who met young scientist engineers to force discussions about layout details and 'tricks', which are usually not discussed at large conferences and were very helpful for successfully designing and operating beam instrumentation. Therefore, the planned workshops were postponed, hoping for in-person meetings in autumn 2020 to spring 2021. As it turned out that this was impossible, online workshops were organized. This format had the advantage that significantly more delegates participated, particularly from China, Japan, and Korea. In this sense, the scope was even widened, and the project ARIES is now well-known in the worldwide instrumentation community. However, a delay for ARIES-ADA was caused by the change of the workshop format and the related scope modification. Further workshops were initially planned but could not be realized in the remaining time frame.

To conclude: Thanks to the funding by the EU, the project ARIES-ADA organized special topic workshops covering actual subjects of great importance, strengthened the collaboration due to the workshops and the exchange of personnel, and were very positively recognized by the beam instrumentation community.

In the main text, the individual workshops are briefly summarised. A detailed workshop summary is attached for each workshop. It serves as an introduction to the individual contributions and is also published on the corresponding workshop INDICO-site. As different authors wrote the text, the style and length varied.

2. Task 1 on Work-package Coordination

The task leaders jointly executed the work-package coordination. Several informal meetings took place at conferences or other meetings of the related persons. For each workshop, dedicated teams were built together with the experts on the topic. Several non-beneficiary institutes contributed significantly, such as CIEMAT, ELETTRA, ESRF, FNAL, J-PARC, KEK, PSI, SOLARIS, SOLEIL, SNS, TRIUMF; in this sense, the work-package transformed into a successful international activity.

3. Progress in Beam Diagnostics for Hadron LINACs (Task 2)

3.1 WORKSHOP ON 'SIMULATION, DESIGN & OPERATION OF IONIZATION PROFILE MONITORS'

In May 2017, a Topical Workshop at GSI concerning '[Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors](http://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/)' (<http://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/>) with 33 participants from Europe, North America and Asia. It was organized as a joint event of Task 8.2 (hadron LINACs) and 8.3 (hadron synchrotrons). An Ionization Profile Monitor (IPM) is based on spatially resolving the ions or electrons generated from residual gas ionization via beam impact. These monitors deliver the beam profile in a non-destructive manner with a spatial resolution of typically 50 μm and time gating down to the 10 ns level. They are installed at both hadron LINACs and synchrotrons. Due to the increase in the beam power of future LINACs (e.g. at CERN, ESS, FAIR, ISIS) these IPMs will substitute the traditional invasive wire-based diagnostics. Even though the principle is well known, there are many technical challenges for such beam instrumentation's stable and reliable operation. The experts in the field presented the experience and technical solutions from installations worldwide. The results were extensively discussed, and the related contributions serve as a comprehensive catalogue of such systems.

The workshop's primary purpose was to introduce the community to a recently completed simulation code called IPMSim, <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/IPMSim/>. This code was produced with the input of several experts to simulate the related physical processes (cross-section for electron and ion production) under various conditions (beam distribution, space charge, external field configurations) from non-relativistic beams at LINACs to highly energetic beams at synchrotrons. The code features a modern programming style, a user-friendly GUI and can easily be expanded to include new physical models and applications. The code is freely available, and its benchmarking was successfully demonstrated. Further extensions of the code (e.g. for Beam Induced Fluorescence Monitors) are now realized. Possible experimental verifications of such simulations were put forward at this workshop, and several have now been performed.

As foreseen in the ARIES proposal, an exchange of personnel was made possible, with Dr. J. Zagel from Fermilab (USA) staying at GSI for several weeks to discuss IPM related topics and possible improvements to these systems at GSI.

3.2 WORKSHOP ON 'SCINTILLATION SCREENS AND OPTICAL TECHNOLOGY FOR TRANSVERSE PROFILE MEASUREMENTS'

The Topical Workshop '[Scintillation Screens and Optical Technology for transverse Profile Measurements](https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/>) took place in April 2019 in Krakow, Poland with 49 participants organized by GSI in collaboration with the Polish Light Source SOLARIS. It was a joint event of all tasks as scintillation screens are installed at almost every type of accelerator, including laser-plasma accelerators. Industrial partners contributed with three scientific talks. The

workshop included an industrial exhibition with four booths. A guided tour at SOLARIS took place on the third day.

The first topic of the workshop was related to the understanding of the scintillation process. Experts in inorganic scintillation research presented two overview talks discussing scintillator physics and recent technological developments. The regular application of scintillators at high energy physics, medical imaging or homeland security is focused on high sensitivity with a low count rate. In contrast to the application in beam instrumentation, the screen is directly irradiated by the primary beam, which might have a high flux within short bunches (e.g. at FEL facilities) or with high energy deposition (e.g. at ion facilities). Several scintillation materials were investigated for various beam parameters, and the results from several facilities were presented.

To achieve the required resolution for the profile measurements, dedicated optics has to be installed in the vicinity of the beam pipe. Detailed optical realizations were presented depicting solutions for these unusual geometries (e.g. Scheimpflug orientation). The advanced technical realizations at 3rd and 4th generation light sources were shown, and related experiences were discussed, including the suppression of coherent optical transition radiation.

The existing camera technologies were summarised by an industrial producer of high-performance cameras showing the pro and cons of the various sensor types. Radiation hardness tests of cameras were performed at CHARM@CERN, showing the requirements for novel cameras that survive the typical radiation levels at hadron facilities. Additionally, the usage of optical fibres was discussed.

A large fraction of the contributions discussed the properties of the different scintillators for hadron and electron beams. Experimental and theoretical investigations were presented concerning radiation damage by hadron beams, e.g. relevant for the target diagnostics at SNS and ESS. For intense electron beams, e.g. at DESY XFEL saturations effect were observed, and an explanation model was developed. The technical realization and the experiences at various facilities were discussed.

3.3 WORKSHOP ON 'EXPERIENCES DURING HADRON LINAC COMMISSIONING.'

The Topical Workshop '[Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning](https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229/)' (<https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229/>) took place in January 2021 as a remote event jointly organized by CIEMAT and GSI comprising of five half-day sessions. 239 delegates registered, and about 100 people were simultaneously connected; see graphic in the detailed summary part. The interest by the community, as measured by the number of delegates, was significantly larger than anticipated. Initially, the workshop was planned for June 2020 as an in-person event.

Several proton and ion LINACs were commissioned in the past years, such as LINAC4, PIP-II, SARAF, Spiral2, or are in the commissioning phase, such as ESS FRIB, HELIAC, LIPAc. Even at existing LINACs, such as BNL, GSI, J-PARC, SNS, significant developments are ongoing, and reports on the related experiences are of mutual interest. The aims of this workshop were:

- Bring together instrument designers, experts, and research groups working on proton or ion linear accelerators' commissioning.
- Review the experiences on the commissioning of hadron LINACs from the first day of operation to more regular operation.

- Discuss the discrepancies between the beam instruments requirements specified at the design phase and the real needs and applications requirements during commissioning.
- Explore the feedback about the LINAC layout and usage of diagnostics test benches during stage-based commissioning.

Most of the contributions were given by experts responsible for the commissioning and operation of the LINACs. The speakers described the requirements formulated for the day-one operation to the time of regular operation and detailed accelerator physics investigations.

The experiences during step-wise commissioning (enabling detailed accelerator-physics investigations) were described and weighted to the quicker installation phase by installing a significant part of the LINAC in one step. For both attempts, the methodology was supported with various examples. These were essential statements for the beam diagnostics community for an appropriate instrumentation layout.

The use of various beam instrumentation was discussed with its data acquisition systems and graphical user interfaces. The potential for automatic beam alignment was investigated at several facilities using different methods, ranging from traditional deterministic algorithms to machine learning applications as a trendsetting topic. The realization and usage caused some controversial discussions.

On the fifth day, several speakers presented special instruments, which have, or will have, applications for operation and accelerator-physics investigations. Further speakers discussed the perspective of industry producing beam instrumentation or a significant part of a LINAC facility.

3.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The objective of the initial proposal aims for the reduction of losses and a safe operation of high power LINACs. This goal is reached, as several relevant topics related to non-invasive measurement techniques were discussed and are now improved. In particular, this concerns the non-invasive transverse profile measurement technology (discussed at the workshop section 3.1), applications for phase measurement (discussed at the third workshop, section 3.3), and automated beam manipulation techniques including machine learning algorithms (partly covered at the workshop section 3.3).

Non-invasive profile measurements are non-standard methods at high current LINACs but are required to allow for the observation of the entire macro-pulse; contrary to SEM-Grids or wire scanners that require a shortening of the macro-pulse to prevent for overheating. One subject of the topic workshop (section 3.1) was the technical realizations for IPMs at different facilities and information about construction details. As the main topic, the simulation code IPMSim were introduced to the community. In the time between the workshop (May 2017) and the drafting of the report (mid-2021), the code is significantly enhanced and now used at different labs. The code also includes the simulation of further non-invasive profile measurements such as Beam Induced

Fluorescence. Moreover, it can serve as a basis for supervised machine learning correction algorithms required for very intense beams at hadron LINACs and synchrotrons.

At the second workshop (section 3.2), applications for all types of accelerators related to scintillation screens were discussed. The general understanding of the process and its applicability was the workshop's main topic. Screens are applied regularly for profile measurements for hadron LINACs of low and medium intensities. The achievable light yield and possible radiation damage are of importance, and the workshop contributed to the understanding of the related physical processes enabling an appropriate choice of the scintillation material. For high current LINACs, pepper-pot emittance relay on the usage of screens, and innovative proposals were discussed. In addition, the applicability of scintillation screens for laser-accelerated beams were presented. Innovative camera technology for low light detection was an additional topic. Radiation hardness differs for several scintillator materials, and an appropriate choice is of great relevance at high power hadron LINACs.

The third workshop (section 3.3) concerned the central topic for beam instrumentation and their usage during the LINAC commissioning, and first stages of operation. People from instrumentation, operation and beam dynamics contributed in a balanced manner. It is interesting to note that phase measurements are vital to achieve the matching between the accelerating cavities and serve as one of the essential alignment tools. Automatic cavity amplitude and phase alignment methods were successfully applied at several facilities. First trials concerning automatic beam steering based on machine learning were discussed, proving the applicability of modern techniques. The improvement of those technologies is one of the objectives of ARIES-ADA. In general, the comparison of achievements at various facilities serves as a solid basis for future LINACs and their commissioning.

The workshop on mechanical issues (summarized below in section 4.3) contained many aspects relevant for hadron LINACs. This concerns, e.g. the production of SEM-Grid and wire scanners using Carbon Nano Tubes. Moreover, adaptive manufacturing is demonstrated with these instruments leading to an optimized production method; the vacuum requirements can be fulfilled. Novel methods for blackening of vacuum chambers are of great relevance for the non-invasive profile measurement method by Beam Induced Fluorescence. This photon detection method is an alternative to IPMs and brought into operation at several LINACs in the last years. Magnetically controlled vacuum drives are an excellent alternative to bellow-based drives due to their enhanced lifetime.

4. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for Hadron Synchrotrons (Task 3)

4.1 WORKSHOP ON 'EXTRACTING INFORMATION FROM ELECTROMAGNETIC MONITORS IN HADRON ACCELERATORS'

A topical workshop with 32 participants on '[Extracting Information from electromagnetic monitors in Hadron Accelerators](https://indico.cern.ch/event/705430/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/705430/>) took place in May 2018 at CERN. The goal was to strengthen the collaboration between the beam dynamics and beam instrumentation community as both communities have to contribute to a correct interpretation of advanced beam measurement methods. Additionally, people working at circular light sources participated as the topic is equally essential for the electron- and hadron synchrotrons.

The workshop focused on various measurement methods of lattice parameters at synchrotrons, such as the machine tune and chromaticity. Recent results concerning betatron-function measurement and beta-beating determination were discussed. The different methods used for optics measurements were summarised in an overview talk. It was shown that part of the progress is related to improvements in the BPM readout's achievable accuracy. The applicability of methods leading to significant noise reduction of the BPM data was demonstrated in several contributions. Moreover, the determination of advanced parameters such as intensity-dependent tune shift and tune spread determined via quadrupolar oscillations is a hot topic and intensively discussed between instrumentation and beam dynamics experts. A comparison between simulations and measurements at CERN PS shows a good correspondence, as had been depicted in one of the contributions.

Further on, Schottky signal analysis was discussed in several contributions. This method enables the observation of many parameters such as momentum spread, tune, chromaticity without any influence on the beam. The applicability for coasting and bunched beams for daily operation and detailed machine studies were discussed. The advanced Schottky system at LHC was recently commissioned and enabled online determination, e.g. of tune and chromaticity. Using Schottky analysis, it is possible to perform BPM-based position measurements for coasting beams. The collection of all those contributions serve as a comprehensive collection of the standard and advanced applications.

4.2 WORKSHOP ON 'NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS'

The Topical Workshop on '[Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems](https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/>) was organized as a joint event between task 8.3 (hadron synchrotron) and 8.4 (circular light sources). It took place in Barcelona in November 2018 with 84 participants. The first day was related to the analogue and digital electronics for BPMs at hadron synchrotrons, the second day as a joint event related to the closed orbit feedback systems and the third day with the subject of bunch-by-bunch feedback system at light sources to cure instabilities. Industrial partners contributed with two scientific talks.

The design considerations of analogue and digital electronics for the BPMs at hadron synchrotrons were presented on the first day. In particular, the methods to achieve the required resolution and

accuracy were discussed. Here the injection of a 'pilot tone' seems to be an excellent method; it is based on the injection of a signal beside the acceleration frequency band followed by appropriate filtering to distinguish between the injected signal and the beam signal. Further realizations of analogue electronics were discussed. An alternative to commercial products was shown for digital electronics based on 'open hardware repository' www.ohwr.org (hardware solutions can be copied under a GNU-type licence); GSI and Brazilian Light Source reported on positive experiences.

The closed orbit feedback system at electron and hadron synchrotrons was compared on the second day. Many familiar aspects exist, even though the applications seem to be different: At electron synchrotrons, mainly mechanical vibrations lead to closed orbit distortions, while hysteresis effects are more critical at hadron booster rings. An increase of the feedback bandwidth is envisaged for the next-generation light sources to improve the damping rate significantly. Presently, the latency for the feedback system is mainly given by the bandwidth of the corrector power suppliers; a contribution from PSI summarised their power supplier developments. Further on, the controller types and the mathematical basis for the inversion of the orbit response matrix were discussed, and the applicability of novel feedback algorithms was reported based on general symmetry considerations on Discrete Fourier Transformation, which have some advantages over the traditional Singular Value Decomposition.

The third day was devoted to the fast, bunch-by-bunch feedback system. A general overview was given in a talk by an industrial partner. The different realizations at the various facilities were discussed using either commercial hardware or unique homemade designs. The feedback system can also be used to monitor the beam's growth rates for detailed machine studies.

A related exchange of personnel took place in June 2018 by the GSI employee Sajjad Hussain Mirza to work for two weeks at the UK Diamond Light Source on topics related to closed orbit feedback. The collaboration led to a peer-reviewed journal article [5].

4.3 WORKSHOP ON 'MATERIALS AND ENGINEERING FOR PARTICLE ACCELERATOR BEAM DIAGNOSTIC INSTRUMENTS'

The Topical Workshop '[Materials and Engineering for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments](https://indico.cern.ch/event/863675/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/863675/>) was organized by CERN and GSI in connection the Department of Engineering Science of University-Oxford and concerned all ARIES-ADA tasks. It took place as a remote event in June 2021 for three half-days. 205 delegates were registered, and about 100 people participated simultaneously, see graphic in the detailed workshop summary.

As a novelty for these workshops, the speakers of the individual sessions were asked to enter separate breakout rooms to enable a discussion with interested workshop participants. As the workshop's topics are not very frequently presented at conferences, the individual private discussions were intensively used to clarify details and enable personal contacts. This procedure was very well accepted, and intense discussions on dedicated topics were executed.

Initially, the workshop was planned as an in-person meeting in Oxford end of March 2020 with 50 participants and 32 talks. However, it was cancelled only two weeks in advance due to the pandemic's start in Europe.

The workshop was targeted to the design and technology of physical instruments, which receives relatively little coverage in conferences and existing scientific literature. This finding might be caused by the fact that engineers rarely participate in regular conferences; however, most contributions were given by the engineers working on the beam instrument design in this workshop. The focus was on advanced mechanical concepts, design and technologies for realizations. The discussed topics were related to:

- Novel materials and production, e.g. ultra-thin wires for wire scanners and SEM-Grid
- Novel materials for vacuum installations with improved properties
- Precise vacuum installations and drives, e.g. magnetically coupled
- Improved methods for mechanical development & production, e.g. 3-d printing
- Review the state-of-the-art materials & production technologies.

The first topic of the workshops concerned wire scanners and SEM-Grids. Even though this seems to be an old technology, the challenge for linear light sources is the production of thin wires in the order of only 1 μm , which was realized for SwissFEL and FERMI and successfully tested. With this technology, beam sizes down to 0.5 μm can be resolved. For the fast wire scanner, as, e.g. used at CERN synchrotrons, the stability of the wire is an issue due to the enormous acceleration to a velocity of 20 m/s and the thermal resilience related to the immense beam power. The usage of novel Carbon Nano Tubes is a solution investigated with several methods at CERN and University-Oxford. The design of the motor, vacuum components and position reading have to use novel techniques as well.

Adaptive manufacturing by 3D printing of the fast scanner's wire fork was demonstrated as a mechanically complex device; the forks are now in regular operation. The vacuum compatibility of the 3D printed devices was demonstrated. Practical experiences for the 3d printing process were discussed in a separate talk, showing the applicability of this method for several further examples. The production method of SEM-Grid at CERN was discussed to produce an equally stressed wire array. Moreover, good experiences were reported for in-vacuum usage of so-called flex PCBs for the insulated connection between the SEM-Grid and the vacuum flange.

Two further applications of Nano Tubes were introduced at the workshop. The first application concerns the blackening of vacuum components; as reported by the company Vantablack, reflections below 0.1 % can be achieved. Secondly, a scintillator can be produced from boron-nitride for transverse profile measurements; functional tests with electron and ion beams were executed, proving the superior functionality.

The manufacturer described a novel generation of vacuum drives using magnetical coupling. The achievements are related to low magnetic stray fields, achievable precision of the movement, and ultra-high vacuum compatibility using novel grease-free metal rolling bearing. Detailed outgassing measurements of polymers were discussed, giving a good overview of the usability of insulators for in-vacuum installations. New sealing technologies for large vacuum flanges were successfully tested at DESY. Moreover, the proposed substitution of the regular stainless steel 316NL by 'Alloy 50' is used for ultra-high vacuum applications.

4.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The objective of this task was to establish methods for precise position measurement and orbit feedback, as well as the determination of lattice functions. Both topics were extensively covered by the workshops described in sections 4.1 and 4.2.

The first topic workshop (section 4.1) brought together beam dynamics and instrumentation experts to discuss the information required and achievable to increase the understanding and operational usage of electromagnetic monitors. Innovative numerical analysis methods can significantly improve an existing BPM system's capability. Modification of the recorded BPM frequency spectrum can be related to beam intensity effects. In particular, if dipole or quadrupole Beam Transfer Functions are executed, a theory-based interpretation is required to model related effects. Schottky signal analysis delivers rich information on the momentum distribution, transverse and longitudinal tunes, and chromaticity. As for the BTF, intensity effects modify the frequency spectrum, and the workshop contributed significantly to knowledge transfer between the beam dynamics and instrumentation community.

The objective of precise beam position measurement was one of the topics of the second workshop (section 4.2). Gain stability of the analogue electronics is a complex design challenge to achieve the required position accuracy, and experiences on the engineering level were discussed in detail. In particular, the 'pilot tone' injection method is now implemented at several hadron and electron synchrotrons to improve position accuracy. The exchange of experiences for both accelerator types can significantly improve the realization of next-generation electronics. The 'open hardware repository' can serve as a basis for efficient electronics production. Advanced digital evaluation methods can improve the resolution and the robustness against electromagnetic interference. The topic of closed orbit feedback is comparable for hadron and electron synchrotrons, even though the source of disturbance might be different. The advantages of novel correction algorithms based on general principles (DFT versus SVD decomposition, see Ref. [5]) were described and adapted for the application at different synchrotrons.

The workshop on material and engineering (section 4.3) was organized by this task to discuss modern trends in mechanical engineering, which concerns all types of accelerators. For the synchrotron applications, adaptive manufacturing is of excellent innovation potential as complex structures can be produced; it was shown that the vacuum requirements could be fulfilled. Secondly, Nano Tube material has its applications for wire scanners due to low weight and high mechanical stability; both technologies were applied for the CERN synchrotrons. Such blackening with Nano Tubes was recently installed in the LHC for Beam Induced Fluorescence profile measurements. Further meaningful experiences were reported at this workshop and will support the engineering design of beam instrumentation.

The third objective of this task, namely non-invasive profile measurements, was discussed in the workshop on IPMs (described above in section 3.1). For the transverse profile measurements in synchrotrons, a significant measured profile deformation might occur for intense beams. The code IPMSim can simulate this effect and is recently used for machine learning-based corrections as introduced during the workshop. Supervised learning via Neuronal Network related to image

recognition serves as an innovative method and progresses significantly in the meantime from the workshop to the drafting of this report (May 2017 to 2021).

5. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for 3rd Generation Light Sources (Task 4)

5.1 WORKSHOP ON 'NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS'

The Topical Workshop on '[Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems](https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/>) was organized as a joint event between task 8.3 (hadron synchrotron) and task 8.4 (circular light sources) and is summarized above in section 4.2.

5.2 WORKSHOP ON 'DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 19)'

The Topical Workshop [Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources \(DEELS19\)](https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/) (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/>) took place in June 2019 in Grenoble with 33 participants jointly organized by ESRF and ALBA. It is based on a series of yearly meetings established six years ago. Thanks to the funding by ARIES, colleagues from Asia and America could participate.

As the main workshop topic, multiple projects of new electronics developments for Beam Position Monitors (BPM) were presented. Those new developments are motivated by two reasons: Firstly, the recent progress in FPGA chips open new possibilities and, secondly, stringent requirements for orbit feedback at ultra-low emittance synchrotrons. A BPM platform currently developed by ELETTRA focuses on modularity; it uses the 'pilot-tone' scheme to calibrate the analogue front-end and cable transmission drifts. High performances FGPA and Analog to Digital Converters are used at other facilities to achieve bunch-by-bunch measurements.

Concerning BPM measurement resolution and accuracy, some presentations focused on sources of error, together with proposed solutions to increase BPM performances and mitigate imprecise settings. This concerns online rf-measurements (like 'pilot-tone' injection) and statistical methods to enable a software-based online correction. Moreover, the effect of temperature and humidity on RF cables' transmission was investigated extensively.

As a further topic, ALBA presented a versatile software tool called "BPMLab" to compute the position resolution of a BPM; ESRF presented the software OASYS for synchrotron radiation simulations. Other topics were related to spatially resolved beam loss measurements using a scintillating fibre with modern light detectors (SiPM) at ALBA. Further BLM systems were described. Overview talks covered recent development for longitudinal diagnostics at SPRING8 and a THz diagnostics beamline design.

5.3 WORKSHOP ON 'DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 21)'

The Topical Workshop '[Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources \(DEELS 21\)](https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/>) of task 8.4 (circular light sources) took place in July 2021 as

a remote event jointly organized by ALBA and SESAME as a one plus half-day event. It was the first time the mid-east facility hosted such a workshop of this type. 49 participants from 20 institutions were registered, among them delegates from universities in Egypt and Pakistan and 2 industrial companies.

One topic was the SESAME facility and its beam instrumentation which was not discussed in such detail at previous workshops. The audience was impressed by the progress made for this light source and the use of solar panels to supply the required energy for this machine. This is a clear example of green energy in the accelerator environment. In addition, the workshop included a virtual guided tour at this facility.

A second focus of the workshop was related to photon diagnostics. It comprised the design and usage of X-ray BPMs, which are nowadays foreseen as part of the closed orbit stabilization system. For the novel ultra-low emittance storage rings, such devices will serve as the primary monitors to fulfil the extreme demands on beam stability. The technical realization at Diamond, SESAME and SOLEIL was presented.

Other topics were related to techniques for bunch length recording using visible light, as realized at ESRF, and is now in operation. An innovative image reconstruction method by an Artificial Neural Network was realized for the transverse profile measurement at ALBA. The related method caused an intensive discussion.

5.4 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The first objective of this task, namely the implementation of a performant orbit feedback, was discussed together with the experts from hadron synchrotrons (section 4.2). Combining the experiences from hadron and electron synchrotron applications, an overview of the state-of-the-art realizations could be achieved, and novel digital correction algorithms were successfully applied, see above in section 4.4. At this workshop, the properties of bunch-by-bunch feedback systems to cure beam instabilities were discussed, and their realizations at several light sources were presented. A commercial solution is available, designed by a leading scientist in the field. Improvements of the ultra-low emittance light sources are required, and the network of experts can contribute to the realization of the various projects. The contribution by engineers assigned to the realization of fast signal processing was a major achievement of the workshop.

Even though, the DEELS workshops were established prior to the start of ARIES-ADA, the co-sponsoring contributes to an enlargement of participants from Asia and America. This led to additional delegates and contributions to the topic (section 5.2 and 5.3). It is a success that SESAME (Jordan) contribute now to the workshop (due to the COVID-19 crisis, the planned in-person workshop could not be realized). Accurate position reading is a major beam diagnostic and will get even more challenging for the ultra-low emittance rings. State-of-the-art technical realizations were discussed at both meetings in detail. 'Pilot tone' injection can improve the accuracy of the analogue signal chain, and FPGA-based position calculation codes are shared between the institutes. The inclusion of X-ray BPMs (detecting the photon beam) into the closed orbit feedback is foreseen for several light source upgrades and is a new challenge, and a network can collect ideas leading to first technical designs.

The objective of innovative transverse profile measurement methods was intensively discussed at the workshop summarized in section 6.1 below. For the ultra-low emittance rings, the beam size is only several μm , and the traditional methods are insufficient. Significant improvements of the existing methods are urgently required to achieve the required resolution, or novel technologies must be applied. Various attempts were discussed during the workshop, and a compilation of the present status are summarized in Table 2; more details are described in the attached detailed workshop summary. This table serves as a reference for any future development. The discussion on the best-suited method is still ongoing and await the practical demonstration at several facilities.

Table 2: Comparison of profile measurement methods at circular light sources using synchrotron light monitors in the visible or X-ray range: The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution are given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>circular</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
X-ray Pinhole	7	L. Bobb (DLS)/ F. Ewald (ESRF)
Comp. Refractive Lenses	10	F. Ewald (ESRF)/ A. Snigirev (Kalin.)
Vis. Light Interf.	3.9	T. Mitsunashi (KEK)
Vis. Light Inter. (mask)	2 (sim)	L. Torino (ESRF)
p-polarization (vis)	3.7	A. Andersson (MAXLab)
Coded Aperture	5	J. Flanagan (KEK)
In-air X-ray Det.	9	F. Ewald (ESRF)
X-ray Diffraction	4.8	A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
X-ray (multi/lens) Inter.	4.8	A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
HNFS	130	M. Siano (Milan)

6. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for Free Electron Lasers and Electron LINACs (Task5)

6.1 WORKSHOP ON 'EMITTANCE MEASUREMENTS FOR LIGHT SOURCES AND FELs'

The Topical Workshop '[Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs](https://indico.cells.es/indico/event/128/)' (<https://indico.cells.es/indico/event/128/>) was held at ALBA in January 2018, organized by Task 8.4 (circular light sources) with the collaboration of Task 8.5 (linear light sources). The workshop addressed challenges for the next generation of ultra-low emittance machines and LINAC-based FELs. One day was devoted to emittance measurements at synchrotron light sources and the second day at Free Electron Lasers. Experts working on emittance measurements for other types of machines, such as hadron synchrotrons and Laser Plasma Accelerators were also invited to discuss possible synergies between the different communities.

For synchrotron light sources, the review of present techniques using synchrotron radiation showed that beam sizes down to the 2-3 μm level could be measured through the careful design and choice of instrumentation. These techniques include direct imaging techniques (X-ray pinhole cameras, Compound Refractive Lenses, or in-air X-ray detectors) and techniques based on the analysis of light coherence (visible light interferometers). Since this is at the limit for the beam sizes foreseen for the next generation of low emittance rings, the benefits of more complex techniques such as X-ray diffraction/interferometry and Heterodyne Speckle Fields (HNFS) were also profoundly discussed during the workshop. The workshop concluded that these techniques would need specific beamlines foreseen for their operation.

For Free Electron Lasers, beam sizes are typically measured using invasive methods through the beam's interaction with movable obstacles, such as Optical Transition Radiation screens or wire scanners. It was shown that wires as thin as 1 μm can now be manufactured using lithographic techniques, which allows the measurement of beam sizes down to 500 nm. In addition, the current status of techniques such as laser wire measurements or Optical Diffraction Radiation Interferometry, the workshop also addressed new, innovative techniques such as those using Cherenkov Diffraction Radiation.

An exchange of personnel was organized within the frame of this workshop, with M. Siano (Univ. Milano) staying at ALBA to discuss the HNFS technique and to perform tests in an ALBA beamline.

6.2 WORKSHOP ON 'LONGITUDINAL DIAGNOSTICS AT FREE ELECTRON LASERS'

The Topical Workshop '[Longitudinal Diagnostics for Free-Electron Lasers](https://indico.cern.ch/event/702602/)', (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/702602/>) took place in June 2018 at DESY with 45 participants. The workshop aimed to foster joint developments of longitudinal diagnostics for femtosecond electron bunches and bring together experts working on beam instrumentation and detector development. Several participants working in the field of Laser Plasma Accelerators contributed to the workshop as these novel short-bunch accelerators face even higher demands concerning the time resolution. The topic of transverse deflecting structures (TDS) was intentionally excluded as there is a strong collaboration between CERN, PSI, and DESY on developing an X-Band TDS with regular meetings.

The workshop was organized in 5 working groups to exchange ideas, plan collaborations or measurement campaigns. The first day of the workshop was devoted to discussions within these working groups. On the second and third days, the working group coordinators reported the discussion results, and the participants presented their contributions in poster sessions.

Compression Monitors and THz Detectors: The intense coherent THz and IR part of diffraction or edge radiation emitted by the electron bunches is commonly used as a compression monitor for feedback on the accelerator phase. The THz/IR beam transport, attenuation and detection need to be optimized depending on the bunch charge, profile and repetition rate. Further improvements of a multi-array Schottky diode detector developed by TU Dresden as a THz spectrometer were identified.

Electro-Optical Diagnostics: Electro-optical techniques are limited in time resolution but are entirely non-invasive. Different readout schemes were discussed to achieve single-bunch resolution at MHz repetition rates. Joint experiments were planned.

THz Streak of the primary electron beam: The goal of this working group was to discuss possibilities to streak the electron beam in a micro-structure operating at THz frequencies. The aim is to improve the resolution of radio frequency deflectors by increasing both frequency and deflecting fields. The application to low-energy beams has been presented, and further studies at high-energy facilities were planned.

KALYPSO and fast digitization: The KALYPSO (Kalruhe Linear detector for MHz-rePetition rate Spectroscopy) linear detector system has been developed as a flexible digitizer board to be compatible with different front-end electronic standards for many applications. Requirements for the next improved version were defined by the various applications of the linear detector board.

Laser Heater operation and diagnostics: The aim was to share the experience of laser heater operation and optimization for the suppression of micro-bunching instabilities gained at different facilities. The cathode material of the photo-injector, e.g. Cu or Ce₂Te, seems to influence the micro-bunching instabilities and, in addition to that, on the operation of the laser heater. Further joint studies were discussed.

6.3 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

Transverse profile measurements are a major tool for beam alignment and accelerator development for the linear light sources. Intersecting methods are frequently used but must be designed with great care. One topic is the suppression of coherent optical transition. More complex photon-detection methods were discussed, like diffraction radiation interferometry or the usage of Cherenkov radiation. These methods are pretty complex, and technical realizations are presently ongoing; design ideas were interchanged during the workshop (section 6.1). Another route is the usage of wire scanners with ultra-thin wires produced by lithographic processes. Laser wire scanners based on the inverse Compton effect act as an alternative; however, they are not technically a standard operational tool. One major outcome of the workshop was a comparison of resolution achievement for the various methods depicted in table 3; more details are discussed in the attached workshop summary. The production details of thin wire scanners were one major part of the workshop on material and engineering (section 4.3), where beam-based measurements demonstrated the technical realization.

Table 3: Comparison of different methods at linear light sources. The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution is given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>linear</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
OTR Techniques	1.5	L. Sukhikh (Tomsk)
ODRI Techniques	??	E. Chiadroni (INFN)
COTR Techniques	3.8	A. Potylitsyn (Tomsk)
Wire Scanner Technique	0.490	K. Wittenburg (DESY) / S. Borrelli (PSI)
Laser Wire Technique	0.070	P. Karataev (RHUL)
Multi-Slit Mask Technique	200	M. Kraskilnikov (DESY)

Transverse profile measurements for linear light sources motivated the workshop on scintillation screens (section 3.2) to overcome the image deformation by coherent optical transition radiation. Hence, scintillating screens are presently used at FEL facilities. A given material's scintillation properties play a significant role in preventing, e.g. for saturation effects. Discussion between instrumentation specialists and manufacturers' representatives led to more appropriate customized design considerations. To achieve the required spatial resolution in the order of 1 μm , dedicated optical systems must be installed; the recent realization at DESY and PSI serves as a reference.

The central objective of bunch length measurement was covered by one workshop (section 6.2). It was a lengthy workshop with world-leading delegates and detailed working group discussions. In addition, the workshop included poster sessions. Major technologies were presented: Electro-optical methods and THz serve as complementary methods; the general layouts and technical realizations were discussed in detail. Experiences with laser-heaters for the instability suppressing widened the spectrum of activities with this workshop. The workshop serves as a comprehensive summary concerning the state-of-the-art diagnostics method for bunch length measurements.

Another objective, namely the high precision position monitoring, was partly covered in the related workshop described in section 4.2. Methods like 'pilot tone' injection and other technical realizations can also be applied at linear light sources.

The last objective concerning beam loss localization and fast interlock generation could not be covered due to the COVID-19 crisis as the task leader could not arrange a workshop in a remote format.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

The Topical Workshops within the frame of ARIES-ADA had a high impact on the development of advanced beam instrumentation. World-leading experts participated in the workshops as well as newcomers, who now take over in the development of novel instrumentation; in this sense, a durable network was initialized. In most of the workshops, engineers participated as well; they contribute significantly to the success of any beam instrumentation but, in many cases, do not participate significantly in conferences. The mixture of these experts contributed to the very positive 'flavour' of the workshop and contribute to the development of accelerators. The relevance of such workshops can be measured through the interest shown for each event by the worldwide audience: 32 – 84 delegates for in-person meetings and 49 to 239 for remote meetings. In particular, for the in-person events, a familiar atmosphere was created with senior people who met young scientist engineers to force discussions about layout details and 'tricks', which usually are not discussed at large conferences, which is very helpful for designing and operating beam instrumentation successfully. The program could be adapted to the pandemic situation after some delay by remote meetings. This format led to a larger and broader spread amount of delegates; with the help of breakout rooms, some discussions and personal contacts could still be established.

The obtained collection of high-quality contributions serves as a comprehensive reference summarising the actual status of these fields and proposals for further developments as gained from experience at the various accelerator facilities. In this sense, the ARIES-ADA Network Activity is an essential contribution to the general accelerator R&D. Almost every objective described in the original proposal were addressed and led to enhanced network activities. Moreover, additional topics were discussed in dedicated workshops on scintillation screens and material and engineering issues, which widened the scope towards innovations.

The workshop results were summarised at several conferences and scientific publications for a larger audience. The program ARIES is now well-known to the beam instrumentation community.

It is recommended to continue such topical workshops in future, as it is an efficient way of knowledge transfer and related personal contact. This will lead to man-power saving collaborations that justify the financial budget invested in covering travel expenses for in-person meetings.

8. References

- [1] P. Forck, M. Sapinski, C. Gerth, K. Wittenburg, U. Iriso, F. Pérez, R. Ischebeck, and O.R. Jones, “ARIES-ADA: An R&D Network for Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerators”, in Proc. 7th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'18), Shanghai, China, Sep. 2018, pp. 71-74. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2018-MOPB02](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2018-MOPB02).
- [2] B. Walasek-Höhne, P. Forck, K. Höhne, R. Ischebeck, and G. Kube, “Screens for High Precision Measurements”, in Proc. 8th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'19), Malmö, Sweden, Sep. 2019, pp. 242-248. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-TUBO01](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-TUBO01).
- [3] G. Rehm, "Characterization of Closed Orbit Feedback Systems", in Proc. 8th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'19), Malmö, Sweden, Sep. 2019, pp. 479-484. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-WECO01](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-WECO01).
- [4] R. Veness, R. Jones, U. Iriso, G. Kube, K. Wittenburg, P. Forck, V. Schlott, and D. Eakins “Summary on ARIES-ADA virtual Workshop on Materials and Engineering Technologies for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments”, in Proc. 10th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'19), Pohang, Korea, Sep. 2021, pp. 16-20. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2021-MOOB04](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2021-MOOB04).
- [5] S. H. Mirza, R. Singh, P. Forck, and H. Klingbeil, “Closed Orbit Correction at Synchrotrons for symmetric and near-symmetric Lattices”, Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 22, 072804 (2019). [doi:10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.22.072804](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.22.072804).
- [6] S. H. Mirza, R. Singh, P. Forck, and B. Lorentz, “Performance of the closed Orbit Feedback Systems with spatial Model Mismatch”, Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 23, 072801 (2020). [doi:10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.072801](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.072801).

9. Attachments

The summaries of the three individual workshops related with Deliverable 8.4 are attached in chronological order. As various authors wrote the reports, the style varies, but the text should introduce the workshop topic and the individual talks. More information is available at the individual slides and the references therein.

ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop

Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs

Barcelona, Spain, 29th to 30th January 2018

INDICO-site: <https://indico.cells.es/event/128/overview>

Workshop Summary

Organiser: F. Ewald - ESRF, U. Iriso - ALBA-CELLS, G. Kube - DESY, T. Mitsuhashi - KEK, V. Schlott - PSI, and K. Wittenburg - DESY

Organised by:

Sponsored by :

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under Grant Agreement No 730871

Workshop introduction and goals

The Topical Workshop 'Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs' [9] was organised at ALBA (Barcelona, Spain) on the 29th and 30th of January 2018 with 38 participants from all over the world. The INDICO-site of the workshop is <https://indico.cells.es/event/128/overview>. The workshop addressed this community's challenges in transverse profile and emittance measurements for the next generation of ultra-low emittance machines and LINACs for FEL applications. The first day of the workshop was devoted to emittance measurements at synchrotron light sources can contain 12 talks. The second day covered measurements at Free Electron Lasers with 9 talks. Experts working on emittance measurements for other machines, such as hadron synchrotrons and Laser Plasma Accelerators, were also invited to discuss possible synergies between the different communities and contributed with 3 talks.

Due to the importance of this topic, a detailed workshop summary was presented by U. Iriso (ALBA) as an invited talk at the beam instrumentation conference IBIC 2018.

Introductory contributions

The first talk of each day covered the general accelerator physics requirements and the need for high-resolution emittance measurements. M. Böge (PSI) summarised the requirements for circular light sources and E. Prat (PSI) for FEL facilities. A second type of introductory contribution was given by G. Kube (DESY), who summarised profile measurements at FEL facilities and further single-pass arrangements where a resolution down to typically 1 μm can be achieved. Such resolution limit requires very thin (and therefore fragile) scintillators and dedicated optical arrangements. Such measurements act as a reference for spatial resolution determination.

Emittance measurements techniques for circular light sources

The emittance itself is not a directly measurable parameter, and most accelerators monitor its surrogate: the electron beam size. The preferred techniques to infer the beam size are based on synchrotron radiation analysis due to its non-destructive nature. However, for small beam sizes at low emittance machines, direct imaging techniques are limited by the so-called "diffraction limit", especially when using the visible part of the radiation spectrum. For synchrotron light sources, the review of present techniques using synchrotron radiation showed that beam sizes down to the 2-3 μm level could be measured through a careful design and choice of instrumentation. These techniques include direct imaging techniques (X-ray pinhole cameras, Compound Refractive Lenses, or in-air X-ray detectors) and techniques based on the analysis of light coherence (visible light interferometers).

Techniques based on X-ray imaging were reviewed and compared by L. Bobb (Diamond) and F. Ewald (ESRF), showing spatial resolution limits of typically 3 μm for all today's technical realisation.

Circular light sources such as KEK or Max-IV use techniques based on the analysis of synchrotron light coherence, like the double-slit interferometry presented by T. Mitsuhashi (KEK) or the polarisation methods shown by A. Andersson (Max-IV). There is even a variance of this technique, presented by L. Torino (ESRF), in which a rotating mask is used to reproduce the transverse beam profile, including beam tilts.

The above-mentioned interference techniques analyse the visible part of the synchrotron light, but the workshop showed that a beam size measurement below the typical 2 μm level, the system should be adapted to smaller wavelengths in the ultra-violet or X-rays range. The realisation implies larger experimental setups

(i.e. dedicated beamlines). An example of that is the design shown by B. Yang (APS-ANL) for the APS upgrade, whose emittance measurement is foreseen to be performed in a complex beamline that accommodates both X-ray pinhole cameras and X-ray interferometry. Further details about these techniques were reviewed by A. Snigirev (IKBF), who also presented the challenges of performing diffraction in the X-rays regime and showed recent prove-of-principle tests done in the past.

In Table 1, the experimentally achieved spatial resolution is given for the various techniques. The theoretical resolution limit is not always reached as several techniques are under development presently, and improvements are expected.

Since the presently achievable spatial resolution is at the limit for the beam sizes of the next generation of low emittance rings, the benefits of more complex techniques such as X-ray diffraction & interferometry or Heterodyne Speckle Fields (HNFS) presented by M. Siano (University Milan) were intensively discussed. The conclusion is that R&D work is urgently required for a resolution improvement. A further conclusion has been that these techniques need specific beamlines foreseen for their operation at all facilities.

Table 1: Comparison of different methods at circular light sources using synchrotron light monitors in the visible or X-ray range: The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution are given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>circular</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
X-ray Pinhole	7	L. Bobb (DLS)/ F. Ewald (ESRF)
Comp. Refractive Lenses	10	F. Ewald (ESRF)/ A. Snigirev (Kalin.)
Vis. Light Interf.	3.9	T. Mitsuhashi (KEK)
Vis. Light Inter. (mask)	2 (sim)	L. Torino (ESRF)
p-polarization (vis)	3.7	A. Andersson (MAXLab)
Coded Aperture	5	J. Flanagan (KEK)
In-air X-ray Det.	9	F. Ewald (ESRF)
X-ray Diffraction		A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
X-ray (multi/lens) Inter.		A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
HNFS	130	M. Siano (Milan)

Emittance measurements techniques for linear light sources

For Free Electron Lasers, beam sizes are typically measured using invasive methods through the beam's interaction with movable obstacles, such as Optical Transition Radiation screens or wire scanners, and, hence called "destructive" techniques.

Optical Transition Radiation (OTR) screen techniques, as reviewed by L. Sukhik (TPU), is based on direct beam imaging after the beam impinges on the screen. The resolution is limited by optical properties and can be

described by the method of Point Spread Function. Reconstruction methods are discussed, leading to a typical resolution limit of $1\ \mu\text{m}$.

Acting as an alternative and non-destructive method, E. Chiadroni (INFN) described beam size measurements performed by Optical Diffraction Radiation. The beam passes through an aperture limitation, resulting in a beam size-dependent light emission pattern. She discussed the method for a beam passage through two or slits which results in an interference pattern. This enables Diffraction Radiation Interferometry with the benefit of clearly separating the contributions of the beam size and the angular divergence.

The Wire Scanner technology was reviewed by K. Wittenburg (DESY). In the contribution by S. Borrelli (PSI), it was demonstrated that wires as thin as $1\ \mu\text{m}$ could nowadays be manufactured by lithographic techniques, which allow the measurement of beam sizes down to $500\ \text{nm}$.

In addition to the currently applied techniques, the method for laser scanning was introduced. As shown by P. Karataek (JAI), the electron beam does not interact with a solid (metallic) object but a "light pencil". A resolution well below $1\ \mu\text{m}$ can be achieved. However, this solution involves a significant degree of complexity, and it requires a team of experts to maintain and properly operate the whole system.

Table 2: Comparison of different methods at linear light sources. The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution is given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>linear</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
OTR Techniques	1.5	L. Sukhikh (Tomsk)
ODRI Techniques	??	E. Chiadroni (INFN)
COTR Techniques	3.8	A. Potylitsyn (Tomsk)
Wire Scanner Technique	0.490	K. Wittenburg (DESY) / S. Borrelli (PSI)
Laser Wire Technique	0.070	P. Karataev (RHUL)
Multi-Slit Mask Technique	200	M. Kraskilnikov (DESY)

Summary on further measurement techniques

Figure 1 shows two illustrative examples of beam size measurements down to $4.7\ \mu\text{m}$ using the visible diffractometer at a MAX-IV (left) and scanning a wire of $1\ \mu\text{m}$ at SwissFEL, which allows the reproduction of a $1\ \mu\text{m}$ beam profile successfully.

Figure 1: Left: Measurement and model prediction match a measurement of a beam size of $4.7 \mu\text{m}$ in a circular light source using the visible diffractometer (A. Andersson, Max-IV).

Right: beam sizes of 500nm can be measured using wire scanners of $100 \mu\text{m}$ (Borrelli, PSI).

In order to measure the ultra-low emittance of the future circular and linear light sources, all the knowledge will have to be applied, and a given machine may need to combine different techniques. For this reason, the workshop also presented techniques that are not used widely in circular light sources or FELs, but that can potentially improve the emittance measurements in the near future. For instance, the Heterodyne Speckle Fields presented by M. Siano (Univ. of Milano) can measure the horizontal beam size in an ALBA beamline, and the Cherenkov Diffraction Radiation introduced by M. Bergamaschi (CERN) is also measuring beam sizes in the order of $\approx 2 \mu\text{m}$ at CESR.

The workshop ended with a review of the methods used in other accelerators like hadron colliders or Laser-Plasma Accelerators. The proton beam at LHC (CERN) is now measured using the synchrotron radiation interferometry technique, which was only used in electron machines until a few years ago. Perhaps techniques based on Ionization Profile Monitor (IPMs, widely used in hadron machines) can be used in electron machines in the mid-term future, as shown by M. Sapinski (GSI). Certainly, the diagnostics experts on emittance measurements will benefit from the synergies between the different communities.

ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop

Longitudinal Diagnostics for Free-Electron Lasers

Hamburg, Germany, 25 to 27 June, 2018

INDICO-site: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/702602/>

Workshop Summary

Editors: Christopher Gerth - DESY, Rasmus Ischebeck - PSI, Kay Wittenburg - DESY

10. Organized by:

11. Sponsored by:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under Grant Agreement No 730871

Workshop Organisation and Structure

The fact that the X-ray free-electron laser (FEL) projects European XFEL and SwissFEL had a similar timeline and, in addition, the extremely challenging longitudinal diagnostics for femtosecond electron bunches is only required in small numbers at a few locations in the accelerators led to a small workshop series organised within a collaboration between Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY (Hamburg, Germany) and Paul-Scherrer Institut PSI (Villigen, Switzerland). During the course of this workshop series, several institutes from research facilities and universities with expertise in detector development joined this collaborative effort. This workshop within the framework of the ARIES-ADA project could build upon this existing collaborative effort and attract 45 participants from 18 institutes.

The aim of the workshop was not only to exchange knowledge and present latest results from the individual institutes in this field but to go a step further and foster joint developments by bringing together experts working on beam instrumentation as well as detector development. Several participants working in the field of Laser Plasma Accelerators contributed to the workshop as these novel short-bunch accelerators are facing even higher demands on time resolution for longitudinal diagnostics. The topic of transverse deflecting structures (TDS) was intentionally excluded as there existed already a strong collaboration between CERN, PSI and DESY on the development of an X-Band TDS [1].

The workshop was organised in 5 working groups focusing on different measurement techniques and detector development. The aim of each working group was the exchange of ideas, planning of joint developments and organizing joint measurement campaigns. The working groups were chaired by working group coordinators (names given in brackets):

- 1) Compression Monitor & THz Detectors (Ch. Gerth & F. Frei)
- 2) Electro-Optical Diagnostics — (B. Steffen & S. Bielawski)
- 3) THz Streak of the primary electron beam — (R. Ischebeck & S. Jamison)
- 4) KALYPSO & fast digitisation — (M. Caselle & D. Makowski)
- 5) Laser Heater operation & diagnostics — (M. Hamberg)

The entire first half-day of the workshop was devoted to discussions within the working groups in separate seminar rooms. On the 2nd and 3rd day, the working group coordinators presented the working group summaries, including achievements and future plans, and the participants presented their contributions to joint developments and research results in three dedicated 1.5 hour poster sessions. As a further outcome of this collaborative effort, several articles have been published in conference proceedings and peer-reviewed journals. They are indicated in the following sections which describe the working group topics in more detail.

Within this workshop, a bicycle tour through the 3.5 km long European XFEL accelerator tunnel was organised as well as a Welcome BBQ and a Workshop Dinner in the evenings of the 1st and 2nd day, respectively.

1. References

[1] P. Craievich *et al.*, "Status of the PolariX-TDS project", THPAL068, IPAC18, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2018, doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC18-THPAL068

WG1: Compression Monitor & THz Detectors

Coordinators: Ch. Gerth (DESY, Germany) & F. Frei (PSI, Switzerland)

The femtosecond bunches at FELs are generated in several bunch compression stages by an optimised interplay of the phase of the radio-frequency (RF) accelerating fields and longitudinal dispersion of magnetic dipole chicanes. The intense THz and IR part of coherent diffraction or edge radiation emitted by the electron bunches is commonly used for compression monitors to stabilise the RF accelerating phases. The transport, attenuation and detection of the THz and IR beam need to be optimised for the given bunch charge, bunch profile and repetition rate. Commissioning results from European XFEL and SwissFEL were reported and compared.

Within this working group, the properties of various detectors have been studied at the storage-ring DELTA at TU Dortmund in a joint measurement campaign [2]. A special operation mode of DELTA allows the generation of tunable broad and narrow band THz radiation.

Furthermore, the possibility of utilizing a multi-array Schottky diode detector under development by TU Dresden to realise an on-chip THz spectrometer was discussed. Spectrally resolved detection of the coherent THz and IR radiation allows for the determination of the bunch profile by reconstruction techniques. First results obtained with new spectrometers were reported.

2. References

[2] Contributions by **TU Dortmund, DESY, KIT, PSI, TU Dresden**:

C. Mai *et al.*, "A tunable narrowband Source in the sub-THz and THz Range at DELTA", IPAC18, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2018, [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2018-THPMK098](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2018-THPMK098)

3. Poster Presentations

ID	Name	Title	Affiliation
1	Carsten Mai	THz detector benchmarking using narrowband THz radiation at DELTA	TU Dortmund
2	Franziska Frei	Commissioning results of BCM/CDR at SwissFEL	PSI
3	Christopher Gerth	Compression Monitors at European XFEL	DESY
4	Bryce Jacobson	Bunch Length Monitors for the Superconducting Linac at LCLSII	SLAC
5	Konstantin Kruchinin	Coherent radiation spectroscopy for single-shot longitudinal diagnostics of ultra-short electron bunches	Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Science
6	Nils Lockmann	THz-Spectrometer at European XFEL and FLASH	DESY
7	Niels Neumann	THz detector and DELTA THz source frequency behavior	TU Dresden
8	Andreas Penirschke	Schottky based THz Detectors	Techn. Hochschule Mittelhessen
9	Johannes Steinmann	Fast THz Detectors	KIT
10	Paul Winkler	Commissioning Status of the VIS-MIR Transition Radiation Spectrometer at DESY	DESY

12. WG2: Electro-Optical Diagnostics

Coordinators: B. Steffen (DESY, Germany) & S. Bielawski (Lille University, France)

Electro-optical (EO) techniques can be applied to measure the longitudinal bunch profile. As an advantage, they are fully non-invasive to the electron beam as they probe the near field around the electron bunches. Different read-out schemes were discussed and developed to achieve a high time resolution and at the same time single-bunch resolution at MHz repetition rates. As a result, a joint development led to the time-stretch digitization technique and measurements at the storage ring KARA at KIT [3]. Furthermore, an improved EO diagnostics setup based on a MHz linear array detector KALYPSO was implemented at European XFEL and measurement results were published [4,5].

A further development of an EO techniques, based on a new configuration of the EO crystal and detection of both laser polarizations, by Lille University, DESY and University of California led to the phase diversity technique with an improved time resolution. Results has been submitted for publication [6].

4. References

[3] Contributions by **Lille University and KIT**:

S. Bielawski *et al.*, "From self-organization in relativistic electron bunches to coherent synchrotron light: observation using a photonic time-stretch digitizer", *Sci. Rep.* 9, 10391, 2019, doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-45024-2

[4] Contributions by **DESY and Lille University**:

B. Steffen *et al.*, "Electro-Optical Bunch Length Detection at the European XFEL", WEP015, FEL2019, Hamburg, Germany, [doi:10.18429/JACoW-FEL2019-WEP015](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-FEL2019-WEP015)

[5] Contributions by **DESY and Lille University**:

B. Steffen *et al.*, "Compact single-shot electro-optic detection system for THz pulses with femtosecond time resolution at MHz repetition rates", *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 91, 045123, 2020, [doi:10.1063/1.5142833](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5142833)

[6] Contributions by **Lille University, DESY and University of California**:

E. Roussel *et al.*, "Phase Diversity Electro-optic Sampling: A new approach to single-shot terahertz waveform recording", submitted to *Light: Science & Applications*

5. Poster Presentations

ID	Name	Title	Affiliation
1	Serge Bielawski	Recent results at PhLAM on electro-optic sampling	Lille University
2	Ishkhan Gorgisyan	EO System for AWAKE Run 2 e-Bunch Length Measurements	CERN
3	Alexander Knetsch	An electro-optical depletion monitor for PWFA	DESY

4	Gudrun Niehues	Long-Term Turn-by-Turn Measurements of Long. Electron Bunch Profiles at KARA with Single-Shot EO Sampling	KIT
5	Rui Pan	Electro-optic diagnostic at FLASH THz beamline	DESY
6	Bernd Steffen	EO@XFEL	DESY
7	Christophe Sz waj	New EO Techniques	Lille University

13. WG3: THz Streak of the primary electron beam

Coordinators: R. Ischebeck (PSI, Switzerland) & S. Jamison (STFC, UK)

The goal of this working group was to discuss possibilities to streak the electron beam in a micro-structure operating at terahertz frequencies. The aim is to improve the resolution of radio-frequency deflectors by increasing both frequency and deflecting fields. As a basis, the application to low-energy beams was presented [7], and further studies were planned at higher-energy facilities.

6. References

[7] D. Zhang *et al.*, "Segmented Terahertz Electron Accelerator and Manipulator (STEAM)", *Nature Photonics*, vol. 12, pp. 336–342, 2018, [doi:10.1038/s41566-018-0138-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41566-018-0138-z)

7. Poster Presentations

ID	Name	Title	Affiliation
1	Gabor Almasi	Compact THz-driven electron accelerator	University of Pecs
2	Arya Fallahi	STEAM	CFEL
3	Mozhgan Hayati	THz deflectors using optimized antenna design	University of Bern
4	Rasmus Ischebeck		PSI
5	Steven Jamison	THz deflection experiments with beta=0.55 electron beams	STFC
6	Csaba Lombosi	Segmented THz electron manipulator for relativistic electrons	PSI
7	Barbara Marchetti	Overview Talk: PolariX TDS Development and its Applications	DESY
8	Michael Nasse	Status of FLUTE	KIT
9	Sascha Preu	Arrival Time Monitoring of THz and Laser Pulses with Rectifying Field Effect Transistors	TU Darmstadt
10	Zoltan Tibai	Compact THz-driven electron accelerator	University of Pecs
11	Hong Ye	Electron beam characterization by velocity map imaging spectrometer	DESY

14. WG4: KALYPSO & fast digitisation

Coordinators: M. Caselle (KIT, Germany) & D. Makowski (Lodz Uni. of Technology, Poland)

The KALYPSO (Kalruhe Linear detector for MHz-rePetition rate SpectrOscopy) linear detector system has been developed as a flexible digitiser board to be employed in many applications. Therefore, compatibility with different front-end electronic standards was an important design feature. For instance, the direct use with PC desktop computers was foreseen as well as applications in MicroTCA.4 rack standard. The implementation of a synchronised data recording by utilising an external clock allowed for a flexible adaptation of the detector system to the different time patterns at the various facilities [8].

This joint development led to the successful implementation in several applications at the European XFEL [9] and storage ring KARA at KIT [10]. First realisation of an online measurement of the spectral distributions of the individual soft X-ray pulses FEL radiation at a repetition rate of 1.0 MHz was published in Ref. [11].

During this workshop, the requirements and specifications, defined by the various applications at different facilities, were discussed and an undertaking towards the development of an improved version of the KALYPSO detector system was initiated. As an outcome, the light-sensitive sensor design was improved and the concept present at the IPAC19 [12].

8. References

[8] Contributions by **KIT, DESY, PSI, Lodz University of Technology**:

L. Rota *et al.*, "KALYPSO: Linear array detector for high-repetition rate and real-time beam diagnostics", Nuclear Inst. and Methods in Physics Research, A 936, pp.10–13, 2019, doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.10.093

[9] Contributions by **DESY, KIT, Lodz University of Technology**:

Ch. Gerth *et al.*, "KALYPSO: LINEAR ARRAY DETECTOR WITH CONTINUOUS READ-OUT AT MHz FRAME RATES", TUPP001, IBIC2019, Malmö, Sweden, 2019, [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-TUPP001](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-TUPP001)

[10] Contributions by **KIT, Lille University, DESY, Lodz University of Technology**:

M. Caselle *et al.*, "Ultra-fast Detector for wide range spectral measurements", Proc. of SPIE Vol. 10903, 1090306, 2019, [doi:10.1117/12.2511341](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2511341)

[11] Contributions by **DESY, KIT, Lodz University of Technology**:

Ch. Gerth *et al.*, "Linear array detector for online diagnostics of spectral distributions at MHz repetition rates", J. Synchrotron Rad. 26, pp. 1514–1522, 2019, [doi:10.1107/S1600577519007835](https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577519007835)

[12] Contributions by **KIT, DESY, Lodz University of Technology**:

M. M. Patil *et al.*, "An Ultra-Fast and Wide-Spectrum Linear Array Detector for high Repetition Rate and Pulsed Experiments", WEPGW018, IPAC2019, Melbourne, Australia, 2019, [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2019-WEPGW018](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2019-WEPGW018)

9. Poster Presentations

ID	Name	Title	Affiliation
1	Michele Caselle	New KALYPSO system	KIT

2	Stefan Düsterer	Online XUV Spectrometer at FLASH gets bunch resolved	DESY
4	Daniel Haack	Compression Monitors at European XFEL	DESY
3	Stefan Funkner	High-Speed Bunch Profile Measurements at the KARA Visible Light Diagnostics Port using KALYPSO	KIT
5	Dariusz Makowski	Real-time Data Acquisition and Processing System for MHz Repetition Rate Image Sensors	Lodz University of Technology
6	Aleksander Mielczarek	THz-Spectrometer at European XFEL and FLASH	Lodz University of Technology
7	Aleksander Szubert	THz detector and DELTA THz source frequency behaviour	Lodz University of Technology
8	Meghana Patil	Novel Si-Sensor technology for high resolution and high repetition-rate experiments at accelerator facilities	KIT
9	Lorenzo Rota	The readout ASIC for KALYPSO III	KIT

15. WG5: Laser Heater operation & diagnostics

Coordinator: M. Hamberg (Uppsala University, Sweden)

This working group aimed at sharing experience gained at different facilities with the operation and optimization of laser heater systems for the suppression of microbunching instability and their impact on the FEL lasing process. The cathode material of the photo-injector, e.g. Cu or Ce₂Te, seemed to have an influence on the microbunching instability and, therewith, on the operation of the laser heater.

During this workshop, joint studies at the facilities European XFEL and FERMI at Elettra were discussed. These discussions led to the development of a near-IR prism spectrometer based on the linear array detector system KALYPSO in the wavelength range 0.9 nm to 1.7 nm. The experimental setup and measurement results were published at the FEL19 conference [13].

10. References

[13] Contributions by **Uppsala University and DESY**:

S. Fahlström *et al.*, "NIR SPECTROMETER FOR BUNCH-RESOLVED, NON-DESTRUCTIVE STUDIES OF MICROBUNCHING AT EUROPEAN XFEL", WEP035, FEL2019, Hamburg, Germany, 2019, [doi:10.18429/JACoW-FEL2019-WEP035](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-FEL2019-WEP035)

11. Poster Presentations

ID	Name	Title	Affiliation
1	Frank Brinker	Operational experiences with the laser heater at E-XFEL	DESY

7	Lutz Winkelmann	STEAM	DESY
2	Vanessa Grattoni	Shortening of FEL pulses using Laser heater	DESY
3	Mathias Hamberg	Laser Heater of the EU-XFEL	Uppsala University
4	Evgeny Schneidmiller	Laser Heater at FLASH	DESY
5	Simone Spampinati	Overview: Laser Heaters	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste